

Varieties were classified into four groups on the basis of grain length-to-width ratio. The ranges of variation in hulling and milling percentage in all four groups were similar, suggesting that these characters are independent of grain shape (Table 1). However,

head rice recovery increased with a decrease in L:W, to a 63.5% average in the round-grain group.

Varieties with high head rice recovery and better hulling and milling qualities are listed in Table 2. Accessions 27796 and 27821 may be

better choices for improving these characteristics in long- and slender-grain, high-yielding varieties. In addition, accessions 27790, 27792, 27829, and 27830 in group I; 27802 and 27816 in group II; and 733 in group IV gave 80% hulling. □

Disease resistance

Reaction of rice germplasm to sheath blight (ShB)

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We evaluated 1,200 varieties and lines

for resistance to ShB during wet seasons (May-Dec) of 1986, 1987, and 1988. Each entry was transplanted in 3 rows (2 m long) 21 d after seeding at 20- × 15-cm spacing. ShB infection was rated during panicle emergence and at initiation of ripening.

Each entry was also tested in the laboratory through artificial

inoculation (detached leaf method) with isolates of *Thanatephorus cucumeris*. Of the lines evaluated, 19 showed good tolerance for ShB (see table). Considering days to 50% flowering, plant height, panicle numbers, panicle length, and yield, HM34-6-4-F and F47 appear promising. □

Promising rice cultivars with tolerance for ShB and their agronomic traits in Andaman, India. 1986-88 wet seasons.^a

Cultivar	Cross	Disease score ^b		Days to 50% flowering	Height (cm)	Panicles /plant (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Yield/plant (g)
		Field	Laboratory					
HM23-3	IR29/Rasi	4	2	90	122.8	6.2	23.6	20.1
HM33A-2-1-1-2F	Mirikrak/Ngoba	3	4	94	114.3	5.9	24.3	20.8
HM22-25-7-121	IR29/Ngoba	5	2	96	116.3	6.4	24.4	20.7
DR92	Released variety	5	3	98	123.8	8.5	26.0	22.2
F47	CCI47F-112-18-4-106	1	1	92	113.7	6.5	22.4	19.4
HM33A-21-2	Mirikrak/Ngoba	2	1	92	113.2	6.5	22.5	19.2
HM37-16-7-110-1	DR92/Pusa 33	3	3	68	116.2	6.8	18.2	18.8
HM22-18-1-132	IR29/Ngoba	3	2	113	125.3	8.9	23.5	16.8
HM46-1-21-F	IR28/Pawnbuh/IR28	3	1	98	121.2	8.2	23.8	13.9
HM23-2	IR29/Rasi	4	1	94	116.7	4.4	20.8	13.4
HM22-2-5-402	IR29/Ngoba	4	1	108	108.5	8.6	23.1	23.1
HM131-1-33	Mirikrak/Rasi	2	1	105	109.4	8.7	21.6	13.1
HM34-6-1-1	Mirikrak/Rasi	4	1	90	109.1	8.7	22.8	17.4
HM34-6-4-F	Mirikrak/Rasi	1	1	88	112.7	8.9	24.9	28.5
HM44-30-7-1	IR28/Ngoba/IR28	2	2	90	108.7	7.4	24.0	16.3
HM16-2-6-1	IR29/Ngoba	3	1	88	119.1	8.3	19.6	12.3
HM33A-5-7-F	Mirikrak/Ngoba	2	3	86	103.3	7.1	21.8	12.8
HM19-7	IR29/Khonorullo	4	3	98	116.6	6.2	26.1	19.0
HM22-23-4	IR29/Ngoba	2	5	95	110.6	6.0	22.0	15.7
Mashuri (local check)	Released variety	7	3	112	144.0	6.8	22.5	19.9

^a Data are means of 1986, 1987, and 1988. ^b Standard evaluation system for rice.

Genetic sources for resistance to rice blast (BI) caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. in Guilan Province, Iran

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We tested 1,265 rice cultivars in B1 screening nurseries at Rasht, Roudsar, and Bandar-Anzali 1978-84. In addition to natural infection, some artificial inoculations were made using conidial suspensions of international races identified in Guilan and from lesions on heavily infected leaves

collected at the 3- to 4-leaf stage from different areas. Each year, susceptible entries were dropped and resistant entries tested against some additional strains the following year.

All cultivars except seven Iranian cultivars were susceptible to the races and strains tested (see table). There